

MOBBING AND TURNOVER INTENTION: A STUDY FROM EMPLOYEES OF THE PROVINCIAL DIRECTORATE OF YOUTH AND SPORTS IN TURKEY

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Abstract:

In this study, the relationship between mobbing behavior and employees' turnover intention in organizations providing sports services was examined. The data in this study were obtained from two Provincial Directorate of Youth and Sports' employees, in Turkey. As the data collection tool, the mobbing scale developed by Yildiz (2019) and the turnover intention scale developed by Landau and Hammer (1986) were used. As a result of this study, in which hierarchical regression analysis was used, it was found that mobbing behaviors significantly and positively affected employees' turnover intentions. At the end of the study, administrative suggestions were given on the solution of mobbing.

Keywords: mobbing, turnover intention, employee, sport organization

1. Introduction

In terms of human resources approach, the selection, orientation, and training of staff for an organization are really costly. Therefore, an organization that has invested in its employees will be able to maintain its high performance only as long as its successful employees keep it in the organization (Shuck et al., 2014). From another point of view, it is inevitable that in organizations that cannot hold their employees, there will be a lot of turnovers and thus service delivery systems will be disrupted and customer dissatisfaction will result (Ashill, Rod, and Carruthers, 2008).

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Recently, employees' turnover intentions have begun to attract more attention from the researchers. Researchers believe that stable employees are effective in organizational success. For this reason, the researchers' studies include the reasons that affect the intention of the employees to leave their jobs (Yi, Nataraajan, and Gong, 2011). There are many issues that affect employees' turnover intentions, mobbing is one of them.

For the first time, Swedish Scientist Heinz Leymann brought up the concept of mobbing in the workplace. In his researches, Leymann (1996) found that working people (with psychological, social and economic consequences) are exposed to a number of negative behaviors. In his later research, he focused on the stages of mobbing behavior and the psychological, social and economic effects on employees exposed to mobbing. Leymann (1996) classified 45 distinct mobbing behaviors in five groups according to their characteristics: attack on the dignity of the person, attacks on performance, attacks on communication, attacks on social conditions and the threat of physical attack. Any of these behaviors can occur due to certain conditions, one-off and limited. It would not be correct to call it mobbing. In order for mobbing behavior to be in question, as mentioned before, long-term repetition of many behaviors entering the mobbing by considering the target is required (Leymann and Gustafsson, 1996). Mobbing is a concept that expresses that an employee in a workplace is exposed to unethical behavior by bullying by another employee or employees (Leymann, 1996). Turnover intention is defined as the employee's turnover intention his job at the workplace (Yildiz, 2013). The separation of employees has costs to businesses. Activities such as finding, hiring and training new staff includes direct costs (Duffield et al., 2014). The turnover intention affects organizations negatively, both in terms of loss of human resources experienced by leaving good employees and dividing the ongoing workflow (Yildiz, 2018).

Mobbing is a phenomenon that can be seen in all kinds of cultures and organizations, and everyone can be exposed regardless of gender (Zapf, 1999). Some studies in recent years have reported that the phenomenon of mobbing is also seen in sports organizations regardless of gender (Karik and Yildiz, 2015; Yildiz, Kepoglu, and Yildiz, 2018). There are many studies that mobbing has lost the peace of the employees in the workplace (Öntürk, 2019). In this study, in order to contribute to the sports literature, it is aimed to examine the effect of mobbing on employees' turnover intentions in sports organizations in order to make the issue clearer.

2. Method

2.1. Measurement Instruments

In this study, the mobbing scale for academicians, consisting of 10 items and 2 sub-dimensions (vertical/horizontal mobbing, and vertical mobbing) developed by Yildiz (2019), was used to measure the mobbing perceptions of employees. Although this scale was developed for academicians, we consider it can be applied to other service sectors' employees. Scale items were measured on a five-point Likert type scale ranging from 1=never to 5=every time. In order to measure the turnover intention perceptions of

employees, 3 items and one-dimensional turnover intentions scale developed by Landau and Hammer (1986), was used. Scale items were measured on a five-point Likert type scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree.

2.2. Sample Size and Procedure

The sample of this study consists of employees of two Provincial Directorate of Youth and Sports (Mugla, and Izmir), in Turkey. The scale forms were distributed to 140 employees with an emphasis on confidentiality and were asked to respond within a week. A total of 110 forms were returned, 7 forms with deficiencies were not considered and a total of 103 forms were found suitable for analysis.

2.3. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and hierarchical regression analysis were used for the data. Reliability of the scales was determined by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient.

3. Findings

3.1. Demographic Findings

Most of the participants were male (77.7%) and married (64.1%). Almost half were between the ages of 26-35 (48.5%). More than half of the participants were permanent staff (53.7%), had university education level (66%), and income of 236-714 USD (55.3%). Most of the participants worked for 6 to 10 years in their workplace (39.8%), (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

Variables		f	%
Gender	Male	80	77.7
	Female	23	22.3
Marital status	Married	66	64.1
	Single	37	35.9
Age	25 and less	1	1.0
	26 - 35	50	48.5
	36 - 45	40	38.8
	46 - 55	12	11.7
Educational degree	High school	19	18.4
	Undergraduate	68	66
	Graduate	16	15.6
Employment status	Permanent staff	59	53.7
	Fixed-term contract	44	42.7
Income (USD)	Less than 535	16	15.5
	536 - 714	57	55.3
	715 - 893	25	24.3
	More than 894	5	4.9
Length of working life in current institution	1 - 5 years	38	36.9
	6 - 10 years	41	39.8
	11 - 15 years	17	16.5
	16 - 20 years	4	3.9
	21 - 25 years	3	2.9

3.2. Reliability Analysis of the Scales

In reliability analysis conducted to determine the internal consistency of mobbing scale, Cronbach Alpha value was found to be 0.915. Cronbach Alpha value of turnover intention scale was found to be 0.843. The values of both scales were found to be quite high.

3.3. Correlation Analysis

According to the correlation results, there is a significant and positive relationship between mobbing and turnover intention ($r = .541$; $p < 0.01$). It is noteworthy that the level of this relationship is high. When examined in terms of demographic variables, the level of exposure to mobbing behavior increases as the education level of the employee's increases.

Therefore, it can be said that those who have a high education level are prevented from coming to certain positions with their mobbing behavior. Similarly, as the education level of the employee's increases, the level of turnover intention increases.

It can be said that employees with a high level of education cannot tolerate exposure to mobbing behavior, so they may consider leaving work (Table 2).

Table 2: Results of correlation analysis

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Gender	1							
2. Marital status	-.110	1						
3. Age	-.135	-.163	1					
4. Educational degree	.072	.110	-.177	1				
5. Employment status	-.039	.294**	-.306**	-.203*	1			
6. Income	.024	-.077	.248*	.492**	-.371**	1		
7. Length of working life in current institution	-.100	-.179	.657**	-.162	-.481**	.303**	1	
8. Mobbing	.103	.017	-.101	.267**	-.170	.185	.047	1
9. Turnover intention	-.082	.081	-.172	.343**	-.059	.166	-.117	.541**

** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$

3.4. Hierarchical Regression Analysis

According to the hierarchical regression analysis, mobbing significantly and positively affected employees' turnover intention ($\beta = 0.504$; $p < 0.001$). It can be said that this effect is strong. When the demographic variables were examined, it was seen that the significance of the education level disappeared in Step 2.

Table 3: Hierarchical regression analysis on the effect of mobbing on turnover intention

Independent variables	Step 1			Step 2		
	Beta	t	p	Beta	t	p
1. Gender	-.126	-1.298	.198	-.164	-1.958	.053
2. Marital status	.027	.266	.791	.011	.122	.903
3. Age	-.150	-1.170	.245	-.051	-.457	.649
4. Educational degree	.280**	2.269	.026	.177	1.641	.104
5. Employment status	-.049	-.410	.682	.002	.017	.987
6. Income	.059	.474	.637	.034	.318	.751
7. Length of working life in current institution	-.021	-.151	.881	-.102	-.823	.413
8. Mobbing	-	-	-	.504*	5.813	.000
F		2.387			7.034	
R ²		.150			.374	
Adjusted R ²		.087			.321	

Note: Standardized beta values were used. *p <0.001, **p <0.05.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This study was carried out to investigate the effect of mobbing behaviors on employees' turnover intention in sports organizations. The findings of this study showed that mobbing behaviors significantly and positively affect employees' turnover intentions. According to these findings, as the mobbing behaviors increase in the workplace, the turnover intention increases.

It is a fact that mobbing has many negative effects on employees. For example, mobbing leads to low organizational commitment (Bedük and Ata, 2019), low job satisfaction (Irak, 2019), low job performance (Rehman, Yusoff, and Ismail, 2019) and low organizational citizenship behavior (Yildiz, 2016). Turnover intention is also an important phenomenon affected by mobbing.

There are many studies in the literature that deal with the relationship between mobbing and turnover intention. Lee, Lee, and Bernstein (2013) found that mobbing had a positive effect on nurses' turnover intentions ($\beta = 0.160$; $p < 0.05$). Akar, Anafarta, and Savran's (2011) research showed that mobbing had a positive effect on the turnover intention of employees in the agriculture industry ($\beta = 0.223$; $p < 0.05$). Razzaghian and Ghani (2014) found that mobbing had a significant and positive effect on turnover intention of academic staff at the university ($\beta = 0.734$; $p < 0.001$). Akbolat, Yilmazer, and Tutar (2014) found a significant and positive relationship between mobbing behavior and turnover intention in their research on hotel employees in the tourism sector ($r = 0.448$; $p < 0.01$). In a study conducted by Yildiz (2018) in an organization providing sports services, it found a significant and positive relationship between mobbing and turnover intention ($r = 0.375$; $p < 0.01$). All previous research results and our study findings are very similar. As can be seen from the above studies, mobbing behaviors, regardless of sector and profession, are an important factor affecting employees' turnover intentions. Therefore, measures should be taken by top management to prevent mobbing disruptions in the workplace. For example, awareness training on mobbing can be given to employees. It can be explained that mobbing behaviors cause both ethical and administrative and legal

problems (Yildiz, 2018). On the other hand, efforts can be made to improve the quality of leader-member interaction. Thus, instead of negative behaviors such as mobbing, extra-role behaviors such as organizational citizenship behaviors can occur in employees (Yildiz, 2011).

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